

KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES, AND BELIEFS REGARDING CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING AND THE UTILIZATION OF CANCER EARLY DIAGNOSIS, SCREENING AND TRAINING CENTER (KETEM) SERVICES AMONG FEMALE MUNICIPAL EMPLOYEES IN TURKEY

Keywords

Uterine Cervical

Neoplasms;

Papillomavirus Infections

Cancer Screening

Health Services Accessibility

Özden Özilice^{1*}, Saliha Özpınar², Türkan Günay³

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to evaluate the utilization of Cancer Early Diagnosis, Screening, and Education Center (KETEM) services and the knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs regarding cervical cancer screenings among female employees of Alanya Municipality. This cross-sectional study included 158 female participants aged between 30–65 years. Data were collected via Google Forms. Knowledge was assessed through researcher-developed questions, while attitudes and beliefs were evaluated using the HPV Testing Attitudes and Beliefs Scale. Descriptive statistics, Mann-Whitney U test, Chi-square test, and Fisher's exact test were used for data analysis. Although 88.5% of the participants had heard of KETEM, only 22.9% had visited the center, and 17.7% had undergone HPV screening. No statistically significant relationship was found between attitudes and KETEM utilization. However, participants with accurate knowledge of HPV screening guidelines had significantly higher service utilization rates. Age and marital status were also identified as significant personal factors influencing service use. Increasing knowledge about cervical cancer screening is associated with higher utilization of KETEM services. However, mere availability of services is insufficient; awareness and guidance activities must be strengthened. The low screening uptake even among young, educated women highlights the need for enhanced public health literacy interventions.

INTRODUCTION

Cervical cancer is a disease primarily caused by the Human Papillomavirus (HPV) and is characterized by the malignant transformation of cervical epithelial cells. It is defined as a largely preventable type of cancer that negatively impacts women's lives¹. Risk factors include early initiation of sexual activity, multiple sexual partners, a history of sexually transmitted infections, early childbirth, immunosuppression, low socioeconomic status, and smoking².

Globally, cervical cancer is the fourth most common cancer among women. In 2022, it emerged as a significant global health issue with 661,000 new cases and 348,000 deaths³. Particularly in countries with limited resources and without established screening programs, cervical cancer ranks as the second most common cancer and the third leading cause of cancer-related deaths among women^{3,4}. The implementation of national cervical cancer screening programs has resulted in a marked reduction in mortality rates⁵. A woman's lifetime risk of developing cervical cancer is estimated at 1 in 116 in the United Kingdom, compared to 1 in 26 in South Africa. The decrease in cervical cancer-related mortality in Western countries is directly associated with the widespread availability of early diagnosis and treatment opportunities. The Pap smear test has led to reductions in mortality of up to 70%⁶. In Turkey, cervical cancer is the tenth most common cancer among women. Its incidence, primarily due to HPV, is 4.2 per 100,000 women. According to 2018 data, 2,125 women were diagnosed with cervical cancer, with 54.5% of the cases detected at a localized stage^{8,9}. Cervical cancer incidence in Turkey was 4.7 in 2003, 4.3 in 2015, and 4.2 in 2018⁷.

Cervical cancer is a type of cancer for which precursor lesions can be identified before the disease develops, allowing for early diagnosis through screening. Therefore, effective implementation of

Volume: 3

Issue: 2

Page: 88–98

Received: 15.03.2025

Accepted: 16.04.2025

Available online: 30.06.2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15835555

1-*Alanya District Health Directorate (Antalya), Türkiye, ozden@ozilice.com , ORCID: 0000-0003-3568-728X

2- Alanya Alaaddin Keykubat University Faculty of Medicine, Department of Public Health (Antalya) , ORCID: 0000-0002-9860-996X

3- Dokuz Eylül University Faculty of Medicine, Department of Public Health (Izmir) , ORCID: 0000-0002-0874-2637

screening programs is crucial for reducing morbidity and mortality rates. Cervical cancer is one of the three types of cancer recommended for screening by the World Health Organization (WHO) and is included in Turkey's national screening programs. Across the country, 284 Healthy Life Centers (HLCs) provide free cancer screenings through Cancer Early Diagnosis, Screening and Education Centers (KETEM). Women aged 30–65 are offered an HPV-DNA test every five years, either through referrals from family physicians or by self-application. Women who test negative are recommended to be re-tested in five years, while those who test positive and have abnormal cytology or are HPV 16/18 positive are referred to a higher-level facility. Women infected with other HPV types and who have normal cytology are re-tested after one year and managed according to the established algorithm¹⁰.

Healthcare utilization refers to individuals' use of healthcare services based on their needs¹¹. Factors influencing healthcare utilization have been described within four theoretical models in the literature: the individual medical care model, the health belief model, the behavioral model, and the healthcare access model¹².

- The **individual medical care model** includes recognizing symptoms, adopting the sick role, seeking medical help, and undergoing treatment.
 - The **health belief model** is based on the individual's perception of their risk of illness and their belief in the effectiveness of health services to reduce that risk¹³.
 - The **behavioral model** evaluates healthcare use through predisposing, enabling, and need-based factors, such as age, gender, education, income, insurance status, transportation, and perceived health status¹².
- The **access model** assesses individuals' ability to reach healthcare providers and the capacity of the health system to deliver those services¹².

Investigating the level of utilization of KETEM services through Healthy Life Centers and the factors influencing this usage is important not only for future regional health planning but also for understanding the health behaviors and needs of the target population. Due to its high prevalence, potential for early diagnosis, preventability with timely treatment, and severe consequences if left untreated, cervical cancer represents a public health priority. Numerous studies in the

literature have examined HPV knowledge levels and participation in screening programs. Studies conducted in Turkey have shown that while women are aware of screening methods, their participation rates remain inadequate. For example, in a study by Pinar et al. (2010), 79% of women reported having heard of the Pap smear test, and 60% stated that they had undergone the test at least once. In the same study, 92% had heard of cervical cancer, but 73% felt that their knowledge was insufficient¹⁴. Studies conducted in rural areas found that the rate of regular gynecological examinations was 26.8%, and the rate of Pap smear testing was 46.5%¹⁵. A 2021 study in Konya reported a cervical cancer screening rate of 33.5%¹⁶. A 2023 educational intervention targeting women attending Women's Education and Cultural Centers and Quran courses showed positive effects on knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors¹⁷.

The primary goal of cancer screening is to reach at least 70% of the target population¹⁸. However, research in Turkey indicates that this target has not been met. Population coverage is a critical indicator of the success of screening programs. A review of the literature reveals no study evaluating the success of the national cervical cancer screening program in reaching the target population specifically in the district of Alanya. Therefore, this preliminary study conducted within Alanya Municipality, where women of varying socioeconomic and educational backgrounds are employed, is expected to provide valuable guidance for local health administration. Moreover, it is important for identifying needs and forming a basis for future education and awareness initiatives.

This study aims to evaluate the use of KETEM services and the knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs regarding cervical cancer screening among female employees of Alanya Municipality. The findings will be significant for assessing the effectiveness of regional health services and for informing future awareness campaigns.

METHODS

Study Group

The study population consisted of 350 female employees working at Alanya Municipality. Based on calculations using the EpiInfo program—with an assumed 50% unknown prevalence, 5% margin of error, and 95% confidence interval—the minimum required sample size was determined

to be 183. Women aged 30–65 working at Alanya (chronic illness, cancer, genital warts), and social structure Municipality who consented to participate were included in (education level, occupational status, income level, family the study. The age range was limited to 30–65 in accordance type). with the cancer screening criteria set by the Ministry of Health.

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Alanya Alaaddin Keykubat University Faculty of Medicine Clinical Research Ethics Committee (Approval No: 1035442-2024/03-15, dated 12/02/2025), following permission granted by the Alanya Municipality Human Resources and Training Department. After receiving ethical approval, data collection was conducted between 17/02/2025 and 14/03/2025 using Google Forms through unit supervisors. At the end of the data collection period, units in the municipal headquarters were visited to distribute KETEM brochures and provide information about health services.

Dependent Variable

The dependent variable was defined as the utilization of health services provided by Healthy Life Centers (KETEM). Participants who answered "Yes" to the questions, "Have you ever visited a Healthy Life Center (KETEM)?" and/or "Have you ever undergone cervical cancer screening (HPV test) at a Healthy Life Center (KETEM)?" were considered as having utilized KETEM health services.

Independent Variables

The primary independent variables were knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs regarding cervical cancer screening. Attitudes and beliefs were assessed using the *Attitudes and Beliefs about HPV Testing Scale* (HTHTİÖ). Knowledge level was assessed through three researcher-developed questions, evaluating knowledge on the appropriate age range for screening, the recommended screening interval, and whether the test is provided free of charge. Other independent variables affecting healthcare utilization were obtained from the socio-demographic-health information form.

Data Collection Forms

Socio-Demographic-Health Information Form: This 27-item form was developed by the researchers through a literature review and includes factors influencing healthcare utilization:

- **Personal Factors:** Age, marital status, disease history

- **Enabling Factors:** Regular and adequate household income status.

- **Need Factors:** Perceived health status, number of days absent from work due to illness or disability.

- **Habits:** Smoking.

- **Obstetric History:** Age at menarche, number of pregnancies, number of live births, menopausal status.

Family History: History of cancer in the family, history of cervical cancer, and history of genital warts.

Attitudes and Beliefs About HPV Testing Scale (HTHTİÖ)

This scale was used to assess attitudes and beliefs regarding cervical cancer screening.

Developed by Tatar et al. (2023), the scale consists of 20 items across 4 subscales and is formatted as a 7-point Likert scale: "1. Strongly disagree; 2. Disagree; 3. Somewhat disagree; 4. Neutral; 5. Somewhat agree; 6. Agree; 7. Strongly agree."¹⁹

The Turkish version's validity and reliability study was conducted by Cangöl Söğüt et al. (2024), with Cronbach's alpha values reported as follows: 0.961 for the Personal Barriers subscale, 0.856 for Social Norms, 0.981 for Confidence, and 0.949 for Anxiety¹. An average score is calculated for each subscale individually. Due to the structure of the scale, calculating a total average score using all 20 items is not recommended¹.

In total, participants completed a 47-item questionnaire composed of the Socio-Demographic-Health Information Form and the HTHTİÖ.

Statistical Methods

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 30.0. Descriptive statistics included means and standard deviations for numerical variables, and frequencies and percentages for categorical variables. Normality of data distribution was assessed using both visual methods (histograms) and analytical methods (Kolmogorov-Smirnov test).

The relationship between utilization of KETEM health services and attitudes and beliefs toward cervical cancer

screening was analyzed using the Mann-Whitney U test due to non-parametric data conditions. The relationship between knowledge level and service utilization was examined using the Chi-square test and, where appropriate, Fisher’s Exact test.

To compare KETEM health service utilization across personal, enabling, and need-based factors, the Mann-Whitney U test was used for numerical variables, and the Chi-square and Fisher’s Exact tests were used for categorical variables. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant for all analyses.

Table 1. Socio-demographic and Clinical Characteristics of the Participants

		N (%*)
Marital status (n=157)	Married	121 (77.1)
	Single	36 (22.9)
Educational level (n = 158)	Primary school graduate	13 (8.2)
	High school graduate	25 (15.8)
	University/	120 (75.9)
Income level (n = 155)	Income less than expenses	51 (32.9)
	Income equal to expenses	84 (54.2)
	Income greater	20 (12.9)
Smoking status (n = 157)	Smoker	37 (23.6)
	Non-smoker	108 (68.8)
	Former smoker	12 (7.6)
Perceived health (n = 158)	Good	81 (51.3)
	Moderate	75 (47.5)
	Poor	2 (1.3)
Chronic illness (n	Yes	49 (31.0)
History of genital	Yes	13 (8.2)
Menopausal sta-	Yes	25 (15.9)
		Mean ± SD (Min
Age (n = 147)		39.24 ± 8.82 (30
Age at Menarche (n = 155)		13.36 ± 1.58 (9–
Number of Pregnancies (n = 106)		2.24 ± 0.98 (1–5)
Number of Births (n = 106)		1.79 ± 0.71 (1–4)
Number of Days Absent from Work in a Year (n = 133)		8.45 ± 1.32 (0–180)
* Column percentage has been provided		

The majority of participants were married (77.1%) and had graduated from university or college (75.9%). In terms of

income level, 54.2% reported that their income was equal to their expenses, while 32.9% stated that their income was less than their expenses. Regarding smoking habits, 68.8% of participants reported that they did not smoke, whereas 23.6% were active smokers.

In terms of perceived health status, 51.3% of participants rated their health as “good” and 47.5% as “moderate.” The proportion of participants with a chronic disease was 31.0%, while 8.2% reported a history of genital warts. Menopausal participants constituted 15.9% of the group.

The mean age of participants was 39.24 ± 8.82 years (min: 30 – max: 67), and the mean age at menarche was 13.36 ± 1.58 years. The average number of pregnancies was 2.24 ± 0.98, and the average number of live births was 1.79 ± 0.71. The mean number of days absent from work due to illness in the

Table 2. Descriptive Findings on the Family Characteristics of the Participants

	n (%)
Family type (n=157)	
Nuclear family	132 (84.1)
Extended family	18 (11.5)
Living alone	7 (4.5)
Presence of another income-contributing member in household (n=158)	
Yes	133 (84.2)
No	25 (25.8)
Family history of cancer (n=158)	
Yes	56 (35.4)
No	102 (64.6)
Family history of cervical cancer (n=157)	
Yes	3 (1.9)
No	154 (98.1)
Family history of genital warts (n=155)	
Yes	12 (7.7)
No	143 (92.3)
Column percentage has been provided	

past year was calculated as 8.45 ± 1.32 (Table 1).

The vast majority of participants reported living in a nuclear family structure (84.1%). Additionally, 84.2% indicated that there was another income-generating individual in their household. A family history of cancer was present in 35.4% of

participants, while 1.9% reported a family history of cervical cancer, and 7.7% reported a family history of genital warts (Table 2).

heard of KETEM, only 22.9% had ever visited the center, and just 17.7% had undergone an HPV test. Among those who had received the HPV test, the average number of tests taken was 1.41 ± 0.73 (range: 1–4) (Table 3).

Table 3. Descriptive Findings on the Use of KETEM Services and Knowledge Level About HPV Screening Test

	n (%)
HPV test: knowledge of age range (n=156)	
20–55 age range	33 (21.2)
30–65 age range	42 (26.9)
35–55 age range	11 (7.1)
Adult women	34 (21.8)
No idea	36 (23.1)
HPV test: knowledge of screening frequency (n=157)	
Every 2 years	30 (19.1)
Every 5 years	49 (31.2)
Once is enough	1 (0.6)
No idea	37 (23.6)
Every year	40 (25.5)
HPV test: knowledge of cost (n=156)	
Correct – Free of charge	148 (93.7)
Incorrect – Has a cost	8 (5.1)
KETEM awareness (n=157)	
Yes, I have heard of it	139 (88.5)
No, I have not heard of it	18 (11.5)
KETEM application (n=157)	
Yes, I have applied	36 (22.9)
No, I have not applied	121 (77.1)
HPV test via KETEM (n=158)	
Yes, I have had the test	28 (17.7)
No, I have not had the test	130 (82.3)
Mean Number of KETEM-HPV Tests (n=28)	Mean \pm SD (Min–Max): 1.41 ± 0.73 (1–4)
Column percentage has been provided	

Only 26.9% of participants correctly identified that the HPV test is intended for women aged 30–65. While 31.2% were aware that the test should be performed every five years, 25.5% believed it should be done annually—indicating a degree of confusion regarding screening intervals.

A total of 93.7% of participants knew that the HPV test is provided free of charge. Although 88.5% reported having

KETEM Health Service Utilization in Terms of Attitudes and Beliefs Toward Cervical Cancer Screening

No statistically significant differences were found between individuals who had applied to KETEM and those who had not in terms of the subscales of Personal Barriers, Social Norms, Confidence, and Anxiety ($p > 0.05$).

Similarly, there were no significant differences in these variables between individuals who had undergone an HPV test and those who had not (Table 4).

The rates of KETEM utilization and HPV testing were significantly higher among individuals who had accurate knowledge regarding the recommended screening interval ($p \leq 0.001$). Regarding knowledge of the appropriate screening age, 42.9% of those who had undergone HPV testing provided correct answers, compared to 23.1% among those who had not ($p = 0.032$). Knowledge that the screenings are free of charge was high in both groups, with no statistically significant difference observed (Table 5).

KETEM Health Service Utilization According to the Health Belief Model

When participants' use of KETEM health services and HPV screening was evaluated based on personal, enabling, and need-related factors, statistically significant differences were identified for certain variables. In terms of age, the median age of those who had applied to KETEM (45.5) was significantly higher than that of those who had not (34.5) ($p \leq 0.001$). Similarly, the median age of participants who had undergone HPV testing (42.5) was significantly higher than those who had not (36.0) ($p \leq 0.001$).

With regard to marital status, married participants had significantly higher rates of both KETEM service utilization ($p = 0.001$) and HPV testing ($p = 0.002$). Other personal factors—including the presence of chronic illness, history of genital warts, educational level, income level, and family structure—did not show statistically significant differences in relation to KETEM service use or HPV testing ($p > 0.05$).

Among enabling factors, the presence of another income-generating member in the household was not significantly associated with either type of health service utilization. As for need factors, perceived health status showed a statistically significant relationship with both KETEM utilization (p = 0.028) and HPV testing (p = 0.007), with individuals who rated their health as “poor” being more likely to use health services. However, no significant difference was observed in relation to the number of days absent from work due to illness or disability in the past year (p > 0.05).

Table 4. Evaluation of KETEM Utilization in Terms of Attitudes and Beliefs Regarding Cervical Cancer Screenings

Scale Dimension	KETEM Application: Yes (n=36)	KETEM Application: No (n=121)	p	HPV Test: Yes (n=28)	HPV Test: No (n=130)	p
	Median ± IQR	Median ± IQR		Median ± IQR	Median ± IQR	
Personal Barriers	18 ± 10	17 ± 7	0.980	18 ± 10	17 ± 7	0.883
Social Norms	9 ± 11	12 ± 10	0.562	11 ± 12	12 ± 9.5	0.825
Trust	38 ± 6	37 ± 5	0.448	37 ± 5.25	37 ± 5	0.920
Anxiety	9 ± 7	9 ± 5.75	0.631	9 ± 6.25	9 ± 6	0.594

Mann–Whitney U test

Table 5. Evaluation of KETEM Utilization in Terms of Knowledge Level About Cervical Cancer Screening

	KETEM Application: Yes (n=36)	KETEM Application: No (n=121)	p	HPV Test: Yes (n=28)	HPV Test: No (n=130)	p
	n (%)	n (%)		n (%)	n (%)	
Knowledge of age range						
Knows	14 (14.33)	28 (66.7)	0.061*	12 (28.6)	30 (71.4)	0.032*
Does not know	22 (19.1)	93 (80.9)		16 (13.8)	100 (86.2)	
Knowledge of frequency of testing						
Knows	19 (39.6)	29 (60.4)	<0.001*	16 (32.7)	33 (67.3)	<0.001**
Does not know	17 (17.6)	92 (84.4)		12 (11.0)	97 (89.0)	
Knowledge that it is free of charge						
Knows	36 (24.5)	111 (75.5)	0.199*	28 (18.9)	120 (81.1)	0.352**
Does not know	0 (0)	8 (100)		0 (0)	8 (100)	

*Chi-square test, **Fisher’s exact test

Table 6. Comparison of the Utilization of KETEM Health Services Based on Personal, Enabling, and Need Factors

		KETEM Application			HPV Screening Status				
		Applied (n=36)	Did Not Apply (n=121)	P	Had Screening (n=28)	Did Not Have Screening (n=130)	P		
Personal Factors									
		Median±IQR	Median±IQR		Median±IQR	Median±IQR			
Age		45.50±13.50	34.50±9.75	<0.001*	42.50±13.50	36.0±10.5	<0.001*		
		N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	N (%)			
Marital Status	Married	35 (28.9)	86 (71.1)	0.001*	28 (23.0)	94 (77.0)	0.002*		
	Single	1 (2.8)	35 (97.2)	*	0 (0.0)	36 (100.0)	*		
Chronic Illness	Yes	15 (31.3)	33 (68.8)	0.106*	11 (22.4)	38 (77.6)	0.309*		
	No	21 (19.4)	87 (80.6)	*	17 (15.7)	91 (84.3)	*		
History of Genital Warts	Yes	3 (23.1)	10 (76.9)	1.000*	3 (23.1)	10 (76.9)	0.703*		
	No	33 (22.9)	111 (77.1)	*	25 (17.2)	120 (82.8)	**		
Educational Status	Primary School	4 (30.8)	9 (69.2)	0.769*	4 (30.8)	9 (69.2)	0.436*		
	High School	5 (20.8)	19 (79.2)		*	4 (16.0)		21 (84.0)	*
	University	27 (22.5)	93 (77.5)			20 (16.7)		100 (83.3)	
Perceived Income Level	Low	8 (15.7)	43 (84.3)	0.102*	7 (13.7)	44 (86.3)	0.259*		
	Balanced	25 (30.1)	58 (69.9)		*	19 (22.6)		65 (77.4)	*
	High	3 (15.0)	17 (85.0)			2 (10.0)		18 (90.0)	
Family Type	Nuclear	31 (23.5)	101 (76.5)	0.510*	24 (18.2)	108 (81.8)	0.741*		
	Extended	2 (11.8)	15 (88.2)		*	2 (11.1)		16 (88.9)	*
	Living Alone	2 (28.6)	5 (71.4)			1 (14.3)		6 (85.7)	
Enabling Factors									
Presence of another income-generating	Yes	33 (25.0)	99 (75.0)	0.156*	27 (20.3)	106 (79.7)	0.082*		
	No	3 (12.0)	22 (88.0)		*	1 (4.0)		24 (96.0)	*
Need Factors									
Perceived Health Status	Good	19 (23.8)	61 (76.3)	0.028*	15 (18.5)	66 (81.5)	0.007*		
	Moderate	15 (20.0)	60 (80.0)		*	11 (11.4)		64 (85.3)	*
	Poor	2 (100.0)	0 (0.0)			15 (18.5)		66 (81.5)	
		Median±IQR	Median±IQR		Median±IQR	Median±IQR			
Duration of Absenteeism Due to Illness or Disability in the Past Year		2±5.25	5±9.50	0.117*	3±10	4.50±8.50	0.879*		
*Mann-Whitney U testi									
**Ki kare test									
***Fisher's exact test									

Family History and KETEM Health Service Utilization

Among individuals with a family history of any type of cancer, the rate of KETEM utilization was 25.0%, compared to 21.8% among those without such a history; however, this difference was not statistically significant (p = 0.646). Similarly, 21.4% of those who had undergone an HPV test reported a family history of cancer, while the rate was 15.7% among those who had not, with no statistically significant difference (p = 0.366).

Although the rate of KETEM utilization among participants with a family history of cervical cancer was relatively high at

66.7%, the small number of individuals in this subgroup prevented statistical significance (p = 0.133). A similar pattern was observed for HPV testing: the rate was 66.7% among those with a family history of cervical cancer, but this difference also did not reach statistical significance (p = 0.082).

Participants with a family history of genital warts demonstrated higher rates of health service utilization compared to other groups; however, the differences were not statistically significant for either KETEM utilization (p = 0.145) or HPV testing (p = 0.225).

Table 7. Utilization of KETEM Health Services According to Family History

		KETEM Application			HPV Screening Status		
		Applied (n = 36)	Applied (n = 36)	P	Had Screening (n = 28)	Had Screening (n = 28)	P
		N (%)	N (%)		N (%)	N (%)	
Family History of Cancer	Present	14 (25.0)	42 (75.0)	0.646*	12 (21.4)	44 (78.6)	0.366*
	Absent	22 (21.8)	79 (78.2)		16 (15.7)	86 (84.3)	
Family History of Cervical Cancer	Present	2 (66.7)	1 (33.3)	0.133**	2 (66.7)	1 (33.3)	0.082**
	Absent	34 (22.2)	119 (77.8)		26 (16.9)	128 (83.1)	
Family History of Genital Warts	Present	5 (41.7)	7 (58.3)	0.145**	4 (33.3)	8 (66.7)	0.225**
	Absent	30 (21.1)	112 (78.9)		23 (16.1)	120 (83.9)	

*Ki kare test, **Fisher's exact test

DISCUSSION

This study evaluated the extent to which female municipal employees utilized KETEM health services and assessed their knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors regarding cervical cancer screening and HPV testing. The findings reveal that while KETEM plays a significant role in healthcare access, deficiencies in knowledge and awareness limit the effective use of these services.

Evaluation of KETEM Service Utilization by Participant Characteristics

The majority of participants lacked basic knowledge regarding the appropriate age range and frequency of HPV screening. Although most were aware of KETEM, the actual rates of service utilization and HPV testing remained low. While 88.5% of participants reported having heard of KETEM, only 22.9% had visited the center and just 17.7% had undergone an HPV test. These findings are consistent with general population data reported in the literature.^(20–21) Despite the center's accessible location in the city center, with convenient public transport options, the low utilization rate may be linked to insufficient knowledge and awareness.

Notably, 23.1% of participants stated they had no knowledge of the HPV test. Only 26.9% correctly identified the target age

group for screening, and 31.2% knew the correct screening interval. These findings suggest that access to screening services is not limited to physical barriers alone but is also constrained by informational gaps. Indeed, many participants reported during data collection that they were unaware of the full scope of services provided or the necessity of HPV testing. Even among those who visited KETEM, some did not undergo HPV testing (22.9% had visited vs. 17.7% tested), indicating underutilization of services and “missed opportunities.” It is possible that some individuals knew of KETEM in the context of other services it provides—such as smoking cessation clinics, dietitians, and psychologists—rather than for cancer screening.

The study sample, consisting largely of university or college-educated (75.9%) and relatively young women, does not fully represent the general population. The fact that awareness of HPV testing was low even in this more educated group suggests that the problem may be even more pronounced in the broader population.

Relationship Between Attitudes and Beliefs Toward Cervical Cancer Screening and KETEM Utilization

No statistically significant relationship was found between attitudes and beliefs about cervical cancer screening and the use of KETEM services or HPV testing. This finding indicates that women's utilization of KETEM services cannot be

explained solely by personal attitudes and beliefs. The literature emphasizes the multidimensional nature of factors affecting cervical cancer screening behavior, including access to healthcare, level of knowledge, social support, and perceived health status.^(22–23) A positive attitude toward the service alone does not necessarily result in actual engagement with screening. Additionally, it is important to note that visits to KETEM are not exclusively for cancer screenings; other services may also attract individuals, contributing to the discrepancy between visit and test rates.

These results highlight that the mere availability of KETEM services is not sufficient—active efforts in awareness-raising, guidance, and follow-up are also required for effective utilization.

Evaluation of KETEM Utilization in Relation to Knowledge of Cervical Cancer Screening

Findings from this study show that knowledge about cervical cancer screening is significantly associated with both the use of KETEM health services and the uptake of HPV testing. Participants who knew the correct screening interval were significantly more likely to visit KETEM and undergo HPV testing. Similarly, the proportion of those who knew the correct age range for screening was higher among individuals who had been tested. These results highlight the critical role of knowledge in shaping health service utilization behaviors.

Previous studies have also identified lack of knowledge as a key barrier to participation in cervical cancer screening. For instance, in a study by Durmuş et al. (2021), lack of knowledge was cited as a major obstacle to screening²². Similarly, Çiftçi and Ünal (2020) emphasized that inadequate knowledge about HPV testing negatively impacts test uptake.²³ Within the framework of the Health Belief Model, perceived benefits and threats, as well as knowledge levels, are known to significantly influence health behavior²⁴.

Furthermore, the fact that some KETEM users did not know the appropriate screening age range suggests that not only the decision to apply, but also effective utilization of services, is closely tied to knowledge. This points to the need for reviewing the information provided during KETEM visits. The high level of awareness that the screenings are free—observed in both groups—indicates that this information is already widely known in the community.

Evaluation of KETEM Utilization According to the Health Belief Model

This study analyzed the relationship between the use of KETEM services and HPV testing in relation to personal, enabling, and need-based factors. The findings showed that certain personal characteristics—such as age and marital status—significantly influenced healthcare utilization. Older age was associated with a greater likelihood of both KETEM utilization and HPV testing. This is consistent with prior studies reporting increased healthcare-seeking behavior and participation in cancer screening with age^{25–26}.

Married women were significantly more likely than unmarried women to visit KETEM and undergo HPV testing²⁷. This may suggest that married individuals are more likely to engage in responsible health behavior.²⁸ On the other hand, no significant differences were found in service utilization based on education level, income, or the presence of chronic illness—likely due to the relative homogeneity of the sample (i.e., educated, employed women).

Among enabling factors, the presence of another income-earner in the household did not significantly affect health service utilization. Given that participants were already regularly employed, this finding is not unexpected. However, previous research has shown that economic independence can play a key role in healthcare access²⁸.

As for need factors, perceived health status was significantly associated with both KETEM utilization and HPV testing. Individuals who rated their health as “poor” were more likely to use preventive health services, suggesting that higher perceived health risk increases engagement in preventive behaviors. According to the Health Belief Model, greater perceived threat leads to higher participation in preventive health behaviors²⁴. In this context, interventions that take into account individual differences such as perceived health and life stage, and that strengthen risk perception through targeted awareness campaigns, may be effective in increasing participation in cervical cancer screenings.

Evaluation of KETEM Utilization by Family History

Rates of KETEM utilization and HPV testing were higher among individuals with a family history of cancer, cervical

cancer, or genital warts; however, these differences were not statistically significant. Notably, the KETEM utilization rate among those with a family history of cervical cancer was relatively high, but due to the small sample size ($n = 3$), the finding cannot be generalized.

Although some studies suggest that family history influences health behavior, the degree to which this factor is decisive remains debated^{29 30}. The present study underscores the need for further research with larger, more representative samples to better understand this relationship.

CONCLUSION

This study evaluated female municipal employees' level of access to KETEM health services and their knowledge regarding cervical cancer screening and HPV testing. The findings revealed that the majority of participants lacked fundamental knowledge about HPV testing and cervical cancer screening. Although most were aware of KETEM, the actual rates of service utilization remained low. Even among those who had visited KETEM, full benefit from screening services was not realized, highlighting the presence of "missed opportunities".

The results also indicated that certain personal characteristics, such as age and marital status, significantly influenced health service utilization behavior, whereas factors such as education level and income did not yield statistically significant differences within this sample.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that the mere existence of KETEM services is not sufficient. More effective public education and awareness-raising efforts, along with stronger referral and follow-up mechanisms, are required. The study emphasizes the need to develop educational and informational programs that enhance health literacy, particularly among young women, in order to expand the reach of KETEM's health services.

In conclusion, it is anticipated that as awareness of cervical cancer screening increases, so too will participation in testing and health service utilization. In this context, strengthening public health policies and community-based education initiatives could enhance women's access to preventive healthcare.

LIMITATIONS

This study was conducted exclusively among women employed by a single municipality, limiting the generalizability of its findings. The sample predominantly consisted of young, university or college-educated women, which restricts the applicability of results to women from other age groups or socioeconomic backgrounds. Furthermore, the cross-sectional design of the study does not allow for the evaluation of changes in KETEM service utilization over time.

The study did not inquire about participants' sexual activity status. Given cultural and religious sensitivities in Turkey, such personal questions, even in academic settings, may be perceived as intrusive by participants. In light of both ethical considerations and the risk of sample attrition, detailed data on sexual health were deliberately excluded. This decision narrowed the scope of the study and limited the analysis of factors related to sexual health.

Nevertheless, this research is significant as the first study to investigate KETEM service utilization in the district of Alanya. The data obtained may inform the development of local health policies and serve as a foundation for future, more comprehensive studies. Additionally, the insights gained regarding the effectiveness and accessibility of KETEM services may contribute to recommendations for improving regional healthcare delivery.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study.

Acknowledgements

No

REFERENCES

1. Cangöl Söğüt S, Küçükkaya B, Cangöl E. HPV Testi Hakkındaki Tutum ve İnançlar Ölçeği Türkçe geçerlik ve güvenilirlik çalışması: Metodolojik çalışma. *Türkiye Klinikleri J Nurs Sci.* 2024;16(3):691-701.
2. Schmeler KM. Invasive cervical cancer: epidemiology, risk factors, clinical manifestations, and diagnosis. In: Post TW, editor. *UpToDate*. Waltham, MA: UpToDate Inc.; 2024 [cited

- 2025 May 8]. Available from: <https://www.uptodate.com>
3. Bray F, Laversanne M, Sung H, Ferlay J, Siegel RL, Soerjomataram I, Jemal A. Global cancer statistics 2022: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries. *CA Cancer J Clin.* 2024;74(3):229. Epub 2024 Apr 4.
 4. WHO/ICO Information Center on HPV and Cervical Cancer. Human Papillomavirus and Related Cancers in the World. Summary Report 2010. [Internet]. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2010 [cited 2025 May 8]. Available from: <http://www.who.int/hpvcentre/en>
 5. Stewart BW, Wild CP, editors. *World Cancer Report 2014*. Geneva: WHO Press; 2014.
 6. American Cancer Society. *Cancer facts and figures 2006*. Atlanta: American Cancer Society; 2006 [cited 2025 May 8]. Available from: http://www.cancer.org/downloads/STT/CAFF2006_PWSecured.pdf
 7. T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı. *Türkiye Kanser İstatistikleri 2018*. Ankara: Halk Sağlığı Genel Müdürlüğü; 2022.
 8. T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı. *Türkiye Kanser Raporu 2018* [Internet]. Ankara: Halk Sağlığı Genel Müdürlüğü; 2018 [cited 2025 May 8]. Available from: https://hsgm.saglik.gov.tr/depo/birimler/kanser-db/Dokumanlar/Istatistikler/Kanser_Rapor_2018.pdf
 9. International Agency for Research on Cancer. *GLOBOCAN 2018: Global Cancer Observatory* [Internet]. Lyon: IARC; 2020 [cited 2025 May 8]. Available from: <http://gco.iarc.fr/>
 10. T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı. *HPV-DNA Tarama Testi Uygulama Algoritması* [Internet]. Ankara: Sağlıklı Hayat Merkezi Daire Başkanlığı; 2020 [cited 2025 May 8]. Available from: https://shm.saglik.gov.tr/depo/Dokumanlar/HPV_Algoritma_2020.pdf
 11. Erdem R, Pirinççi E. Sağlık hizmetlerinde kullanım ve kullanım etkileyen faktörler. *OMÜ Tıp Fakültesi Dergisi.* 2003;20(1):39-46.
 12. Zencir M, Çiçeklioğlu M. Sağlık hizmetlerinin kullanımında ayrımcılık. *Toplum ve Hekim.* 2020;35(2):143-152.
 13. Gözüm S, Çapık C. Sağlık davranışlarının geliştirilmesinde bir rehber: sağlık inanç modeli. *Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi Hemşirelik Yüksekokulu Elektronik Dergisi.* 2014;7(3):230-237.
 14. Pınar G, Topuz Ş, An Ş, Doğan N, Kaya N, Algier L. Başkent Üniversitesi Ankara Hastanesi Kadın Hastalıkları ve Doğum Polikliniğine başvuran kadınların HPV aşısı ve serviks kanseri ile ilgili bilgi düzeyleri. *Türk Jinekoloji Onkoloji Dergisi.* 2010;1:11-18.
 15. Durmaz S, Özvurmaz S, Adana F, Kurt F. Kadınlarda serviks kanserinin tanısına ilişkin tutum ve düzenli jinekolojik muayene ilişkisinin kesitsel olarak değerlendirilmesi. *Adnan Menderes Üniversitesi Sağlık Bilimleri Fakültesi Dergisi.* 2021;5(1):26-36. <https://doi.org/10.46237/amusbfd.727999>
 16. Tuncez İH, Aksoy N, Koç M. Ulusal kanser tarama programı sonuçları: bir il örneği. *Phnx Med J.* 2021;3(2):46-73. <https://doi.org/10.38175/phnx.922780>
 17. Aksungur A, Bağcı HH, Özdemirkan T. Kanser eğitimleri kanser farkındalığını artırıyor mu?. *ESTÜDAM Halk Sağlığı Dergisi.* 2024;9(1):13-22.
 18. Keskinçiliç B, Gültekin M, Karaca AS, Öztürk C, Boztaş G, Karaca M, et al. *Türkiye Kanser Kontrol Programı*. Ankara: T.C. Sağlık Bakanlığı Türkiye Halk Sağlığı Kurumu; 2016.
 19. Tatar O, Haward B, Zhu P, Griffin-Mathieu G, Perez S, McBride E, et al. Understanding the challenges of HPV-based cervical screening: development and validation of HPV testing and self-sampling attitudes and beliefs scales. *Curr Oncol.* 2023;30(1):1206-1219.
 20. Koç Z, Sağlam Z, Avcı D. Evaluation of knowledge and attitudes of women on HPV and cervical cancer screening. *J Cancer Educ.* 2022;37(1):165-172. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13187-021-01933-2>
 21. Gültekin M, Yüce K. Cervical cancer control in Turkey and current HPV vaccination and screening programs. *Turk J Med Sci.* 2021;51(SI-1):28-35. <https://doi.org/10.3906/sag-2101-12>
 22. Durmuş M, Yılmaz M, Yücel Ü. Kadınların serviks kanseri ve HPV farkındalık düzeyleri ile taramaya katılım durumlarının incelenmesi. *Kadın Sağlığı Hemşireliği Dergisi.* 2021;7(1):25-34.
 23. Çiftçi S, Ünal N. Kadınların HPV ve serviks kanseri hakkındaki bilgi düzeyleri ve tarama davranışları. *Türkiye Aile Hekimliği Dergisi.* 2020;24(2):89-96.
 24. Glanz K, Rimer BK, Viswanath K, editors. *Health behavior and health education: theory, research, and practice*. 4th ed. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass; 2008.
 25. Aslan D, Gürsoy H, Yıldız M. Serviks kanseri taramasında yaşın ve sosyal faktörlerin etkisi. *Kadın Sağlığı Hemşireliği Dergisi.* 2020;5(2):94-102.
 26. Lee HY, Kobayashi LC. Age differences in cervical cancer screening among immigrant women. *Prev Med Rep.* 2021;21:101301.
 27. Pınar G, Kaya N, Ayhan A. Kadınların serviks kanseri tarama davranışları ve etkileyen faktörler. *Hemşirelikte Araştırma Geliştirme Dergisi.* 2018;20(3):46-56.
 28. Özdemir D, Bilgili N. Kadınların HPV aşısı ve servikal tarama hakkındaki bilgi ve tutumları. *Uluslararası Toplum Araştırmaları Dergisi.* 2019;15(25):703-721.
 29. Yılmazel Güler E, Çelik Y. Kadınların serviks kanseri taramalarına katılım durumları ve etkileyen faktörler. *Kadın Sağlığı Hemşireliği Dergisi.* 2020;7(1):1-10.
 30. Kısaçık G, Karadeniz H. Aile öyküsünün kadınların rahim ağzı kanseri taramalarına etkisi: sistematik derleme. *Sağlık Akademisyenleri Dergisi.* 2021;8(2):91-98.